

Solubilities of Weak Acids in Salts of Weak Acids at Very High Concentrations.

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Philip (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **87**, 897) and Philip and Garner (*ibid.*, 1909, **95**, 1466) have determined the solubilities of sparingly soluble acids in solutions of sodium salts of weak acids, but the range of the concentrations of sodium salt, they have investigated, is very small and that too very limited. In this paper, we have extended this work and have determined the solubilities of weak acids in very high concentrations of sodium salts of weak acids as well as for very low concentrations of these salts.

Our results of the solubilities are recorded below.

TABLE I.

Solubility of benzoic acid.

(a) *In sodium formate. Temp., 30°.*

Conc., g./litre.

Sodium formate.	Benzoic acid.	Sodium formate.	Benzoic acid.
0	4·033	28·6356	10·920
4·0541	6·339	42·9536	12·297
6·0862	6·964	84·0178	16·348
12·1724	8·404	112·0237	17·885
21·4768	9·838	168·0356	20·325

(b) *In sodium acetate. Temp., 30°.*

Conc., g./litre.

Sodium acetate.	Benzoic acid.	Sodium acetate.	Benzoic acid.
0	4.033	27.3110	17.72
2.2322	5.750	33.6607	19.56
4.4643	7.484	46.4287	23.10
8.9286	10.00	58.0359	25.92
11.0544	11.09	67.3214	27.57
14.5099	12.33	100.9822	33.61
23.7605	16.17	134.6428	38.64
		201.9644	48.17

(c) *In sodium salicylate.*

Sodium salicylate.	Benzoic acid.	Sodium salicylate.	Benzoic acid.
0	4.033	73.0209	7.213
9.4220	4.174	97.3612	10.17
13.9087	4.252	146.0418	13.73
26.5530	5.029	194.7224	22.03
46.6806	5.759	292.0836	33.72
58.4167	6.624		

(d) *In sodium citrate.*

Sodium citrate.	Benzoic acid.	Sodium citrate.	Benzoic acid.
0	4.033	33.2951	19.24
5.3701	7.509	55.4918	25.02
7.9274	8.794	83.2377	30.20
15.1341	12.51	110.9836	34.08
27.7459	17.29	116.4754	39.38

TABLE II.

Solubility of salicylic acid.(a) *In sodium formate. Temp., 30°.*

Conc., g./litre.

Sodium formate.	Salicylic acid.	Sodium formate.	Salicylic acid.
0	2·743	33·2340	26·36
4·6456	8·624	36·0035	27·07
6·8578	10·35	48·0047	32·02
9·0009	12·08	72·0071	39·87
13·0922	15·15	144·0142	63·66
24·0024	21·04		

(b) *In sodium acetate.*

Sodium acetate.	Salicylic acid.	Sodium acetate.	Salicylic acid.
0	2·743	36·4989	31·06
2·3547	4·828	43·7986	36·22
3·5322	6·026	72·9977	57·25
7·0643	9·122	109·4966	77·43
10·4281	11·73	218·9932	147·20
19·9087	19·32		

(c) *In sodium citrate.*

Sodium citrate.	Salicylic acid.	Sodium citrate.	Salicylic acid.
0	2·743	33·2951	29·73
5·3701	7·875	55·4918	43·17
7·924	10·26	83·2377	57·15
15·1313	15·92	110·9836	71·91
27·7459	24·94	156·4754	90·78

(d) *In sodium benzoate.* Temp., 14.5°.

Conc., g./litre.

Sodium benzoate.	Salicylic acid.	Sodium benzoate.	Salicylic acid.
0	1.667	34.6121	4.189
1.7306	2.427	57.6869	4.436
3.4612	3.393	86.5303	4.285
6.9224	3.829	115.3737	4.513
17.3061	4.171	173.0606	5.460

(e) *In sodium chloride.* Temp., 25°.

Sodium chloride.	Salicylic acid.	Sodium chloride.	Salicylic acid.
0	2.478	19.60	2.075
1.176	2.229	29.40	2.000
5.88	2.219	39.20	1.901
11.76	2.150	58.80	1.719
14.70	2.125		

TABLE IV.

Solubility of cinnamic acid.(a) *In sodium acetate.* Temp., 30°.

Conc., g./litre.

Sodium acetate.	Cinnamic acid.	Sodium acetate.	Cinnamic acid.
0	0.6937	36.4989	6.563
2.3574	1.763	43.7986	7.224
3.5322	2.334	72.9977	9.162
7.0643	2.907	109.4966	11.10
10.4281	3.525	218.9932	18.41
19.9087	4.825		

(b) *In sodium citrate.* Temp., 30°.

Conc., g./litre.

Sodium citrate.	Cinnamic acid.	Sodium citrate.	Cinnamic acid.
0	0·6937	33·2951	9·404
5·3701	3·469	55·4918	11·75
7·9274	4·317	83·2377	12·79
15·1341	6·322	110·9836	13·69
27·7459	8·486	166·4754	14·49

(c) *In sodium benzoate.* Temp., 16·3°.

Sodium benzoate	Cinnamic acid.	Sodium benzoate.	Cinnamic acid.
0	0·3914	34·6121	2·997
1·7306	0·7827	57·6868	4·212
3·4612	1·021	86·5303	5·121
6·9224	1·393	115·3737	5·571
17·3061	2·069		

TABLE IV.

Solubility of succinic acid.(a) *In sodium salicylate.* Temp., 14·3°.

Conc., g./litre.

Sodium Salicylate.	Succinic acid..	Sodium salicylate.	Succinic acid.
0	50·23	81·0667	82·94
11·5809	59·00	121·6	93·71
22·1091	63·84	162·1333	97·79
40·5333	70·98	243·2	86·80

(b) *In sodium chloride.* Temp., 25°.

Conc., g./litre.

Sodium chloride.	Succinic acid.	Sodium chloride.	Succinic acid.
0	70·03	313·2777	22·74
17·7001	74·85	316·0748	10·00
35·4003	68·55	319·0124	4·513
44·2505	66·51	321·8218	3·619
118·0013	52·25	327·8713	3·004
177·0019	42·27	333·9658	2·015
221·2523	36·03	347·0611	1·038
295·0031	26·52	354·0038	0·5224

DISCUSSION.

(a) From our experimental results on solubilities it is observed that the solubility of a stronger acid is greater than that of a weaker acid for the same concentration of a sodium salt. It will be seen from the results that the solubility of these acids in pure water at 30° is of the same order of magnitude. But when we consider their solubilities in various concentrations of sodium salts such as sodium formate, sodium acetate and sodium citrate, the solubility of the stronger salicylic acid rapidly increases and is always greater than those of the weaker benzoic and cinnamic acids, although in pure water the solubility of benzoic acid is greater than that of salicylic acid.

(b) When we consider the solubilities of cinnamic and salicylic acids, we find that the solubility of salicylic acid increases more rapidly with the concentration of sodium benzoate than that of cinnamic acid for very low concentrations. When, however, the concentration of sodium benzoate increases, the solubility of cinnamic acid increases with the same rate, although the solubility of salicylic acid increases very slowly and that of the cinnamic acid finally exceeds the solubility of salicylic acid.

(c) The values for the solubility of succinic acid obtained in various concentrations of sodium salicylate are still more striking. The benzoic and succinic acids are more or less equally strong and it would, therefore, appear that the increase should practically be the same in both the cases. It is, however, observed that the increase

in solubility for the same concentration of sodium salicylate is much greater for succinic acid than for benzoic acid. When however the concentration of sodium salicylate exceeds 1M, the solubility of succinic acid instead of increasing with the concentration goes on decreasing, first gradually, and then rather rapidly.

(d) When the solubility of salicylic acid in sodium chloride is considered, the solubility falls first very rapidly with the concentration of sodium chloride and then very slowly. With succinic acid, the solubility increases for very low concentrations of sodium chloride and then gradually decreases.

It is clear from the above observations that the dibasic succinic acid behaves differently from the monobasic acids. Moreover, it should be observed from (b) that salicylic acid also slightly deviates from the general rule. Thus it appears that the increase in solubility of weak acids in their sodium salts is governed not only by their dissociation constants but also influenced by the basicity of the acid; this increase also depends on whether the acid is a normal or hydroxy acid.

If we compare the solubility of the same acid in various salts, it is observed that the solubility is greater and increases more rapidly in the salt of a weaker than in that of a stronger acid of the same concentration.

An interesting relation is observed when we study the solubilities of benzoic, salicylic and cinnamic acids in sodium citrate. Although citric acid is stronger than formic acid, yet the solubility of salicylic acid is much greater in sodium citrate than in sodium formate. Similarly the solubility of benzoic acid is much greater in sodium citrate than in sodium formate of the same concentration. The solubility of salicylic acid is more or less the same in sodium citrate and sodium acetate when the concentration of sodium salt is low, although citric acid is much stronger than acetic acid. At higher concentrations of the salts, the solubility of salicylic acid is much less in citrate than in acetate.

The solubilities of benzoic and cinnamic acids in the above two salts show a peculiar behaviour. For low concentrations of the salts, the solubilities of these acids are greater in sodium citrate than in sodium acetate, although acetic acid is a much weaker acid than citric acid, but with increase in concentration, the solubilities of cinnamic and benzoic acids are now less in sodium citrate than in sodium acetate of the same concentration. The solubility of salicylic

acid at low concentration is the same in sodium citrate, and sodium acetate ; it is greater in case of benzoic acid in sodium citrate and this variation is still greater in case of cinnamic acid. Thus citrate shows a peculiar behaviour.

In case of sodium formate and citrate, it will be seen that the rate of increase in the solubility of salicylic acid in sodium citrate is rapidly falling and if sufficiently high concentrations are taken, the solubility of salicylic acid may become less in sodium citrate than in sodium formate as expected on the basis of the strength of the acids from which these salts are prepared.

The behaviour of sodium salicylate is rather striking ; salicylic acid is stronger than formic acid and it is expected that the solubility of a dissolved acid should be less in sodium salicylate than in sodium formate and this conclusion is borne out only at the low concentrations of these salts. This behaviour is exactly the reverse of that of sodium citrate, in which the solubility at first increases and then diminishes at higher concentrations of sodium citrate.

The solubility of the weak acid instead of increasing on addition of a salt of a strong acid actually falls. Thus the solubilities of salicylic and succinic acids are less in sodium chloride than in pure water.

SUMMARY.

(1) Solubilities of benzoic, salicylic, cinnamic, and succinic acids in sodium formate, sodium acetate, sodium salicylate, sodium citrate, sodium benzoate and sodium chloride have been determined over a very wide range of concentrations.

(2) The experimental results with solubilities show that the solubility of a weak acid in sodium salt of a weak acid depends on the strength of the acid used. Thus when we are considering the solubilities of various acids in the same salt, generally the stronger acid is more soluble but the solubility is also influenced by the basicity and the nature of the acids. Thus the solubilities show deviation from the general rule in the case of succinic acid which is dibasic and in case of salicylic acid, which is a hydroxy acid.

(3) When the solubilities of weak acids in salts of very strong acids are considered, it is found that the solubility in the salt solution is less than that in pure water and decreases with the increase in concentration of sodium salt. Thus sodium chloride shows this behaviour with salicylic and succinic acids.